

Welcome to the February newsletter and this year there's an extra day to enjoy it. Let's leap right in.

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And we start with a lovely endorsement from LNL Steve Samuel

'I love the newsletters, they're invaluable, thank you!'

Steve Samuel, LNL City, University of London

Top Tips for ReproducibiliTea Journal Clubs

Here are some top tips for running a ReproducibiliTea Journal Club or any journal club.

Ways to get new members

- Have a stall at Fresher's Fair - students sign up to a mailing list. Then make the first meeting of the year more of an introduction to open research.
- Get a 30 minute slot during graduate student introduction week – put on a mini journal club.
- Emphasise the social aspect of ReproducibiliTea. When a new person joins the department tell them about the journal club meetings – offer them as a chance to meet people.

Type of paper to discuss

- Think about why you select a particular paper so there are key take home messages/points. The aim is to invite discussion not simply have a lecture.
- Not too long/too dense.

Choosing a paper

- Ask someone to present and they get to choose the paper
- Have a reading list and ask someone to choose from the list
- People vote on which paper to cover – choose from several.

Lower the bar

- Make the barriers to engagement as low as possible. For example the presenter can start the session with a 10 minute talk about the paper so the attendees don't have to read it ahead of time.

Involve everyone

- Be aware of the balance of contributions and work towards making the discussion diverse/ fair /equitable to everyone present. For example if the conversation is dominated by 1 or 2 people, others may feel that there is not much for them to contribute.
- For online meetings – at the start reiterate that everyone should be mindful of the amount of time they take up. Use raised hands. If you are talking and you notice someone has raised their hand, realise that you should wrap up. The chair can/should stop people.

- Sometimes when senior people at the event, others stay quiet, not necessarily because they're intimidated but because they want to hear their thoughts on the matter.
- Good for the chair to say several times during the meeting – who haven't we heard from yet? This makes it explicit that everyone can/should contribute to the discussion.
- Everyone can ask questions of the research – encourage this – for example younger attendees may not feel confident to share opinions but can still ask questions.

Format

- If possible, it's useful to have both a chair and a presenter. The presenter will bring their own discussion points. If conversation is getting thin, the chair can pick up points and drive the discussion. Alternatively the person that presents steers the meeting. Either way make it clear at the start who is steering/chairing.
- Don't want to have the same few people leading every session. For example if have 10 -12 attendees then ideally have a different person each week/meeting per term.
- Good to have discussion points prepared ahead of time (maybe as a slide).
- 10 -15 people is good group size. As the group gets bigger it's likely to become more of a lecture. Might consider splitting into 2 smaller groups.

Vary things

- Invite guest speakers, especially if meeting online, although this means the meeting may become more of a guest talk rather than a discussion.
- When promoting a meeting on Twitter/social media tag the author/s of the paper being discussed. The author can contact the club and invite themselves to attend.
- Have a Registered Report month, especially if someone is studying these/has to do one. It becomes an opportunity for them to share what they've learned.

- Include practical stuff, for example sharing an experience of putting something into practice so that attendees come away with something tangible. Can do this alongside discussing a paper. This can be part of the evolution of the journal club. Can run as a workshop, but this is more work for the organisers.

These top tips have been taken from the 2021 UKRN webinar 'Setting up a ReproducibiliTea Journal Club' and complement the existing resources on the [ReproducibiliTea website](#). With thanks to webinar attendees: Ian Lahart (Wolverhampton), Sam Parsons (Oxford), Adam Partridge (Cardiff), Mojtaba Soltanlou (Surrey), Jan Vornhagen (Copenhagen) and Emma Wise (Surrey).

UKRN Resource

[Open Research: Examples of good practice, and resources across disciplines](#)

Now in its fourth year, the annual update of "Open Research across disciplines" is now available and includes Sport and Exercise Science. Authors: Emily K. Farran, Priya Silverstein, Aminath A. Ameen, Iliana Misheva, and Camilla Gilmore.

University of Liverpool Open Research Week

Monday 26th February - Friday 1st March

[Open Research Practices and Skills-Organised and supported by the UKRN](#)

The following LNLs are involved in this online event: Alexis Makin (University of Liverpool), Michel Belyk (Edge Hill University) Andrew Jones (Liverpool John Moore's University), Osama Mahmoud (recently moved to Institutional lead position University of Essex) and Krzysztof Cipora (Loughborough University). You are very welcome to attend and take part in the Q&A session.

In the afternoon we are holding the first of our UKRN Roadshows as part of the [Open Research Community Showcase event](#). This will include presentations from University of Liverpool Institutional Lead Bill Greenhalf, Local Network Lead Alexis Makin and Open Research Coordinator and

Administrator (ORCA) Alice Howarth - a role associated with the Research England funded Open Research Programme, and our very own Community Project Manager Will Gawned. The Q&A session will also include visiting LNLs.

LNL workshops

Our first LNL workshop - Setting up a student consortium for undergraduate final year projects - was held on 1st February. A recording of Kait Clark's presentation will be made available shortly. Our second LNL workshop is:

[Building LNL – Open Research enabler relationships](#)

Thursday March 7th 1:00pm – 2:00pm

Register [here](#)

Please also add the following dates and times to your diary - further details to follow

- Thursday 4th April
- Thursday 2nd May
- Thursday 13th June

Other events

[Symposium: Critical Perspectives on the Metascience Reform Movement](#)

March 7 2024 14:00 – 17:30 UK time

Organised by the Center for Open Science. Register [here](#)

Love Methods Week - 'love your methods before you love your data'

Unfortunately we've missed [this year's](#) inaugural event organised by the Berlin Institute of Health but they provide resources [here](#). Use #LoveMethods24 to find out how they got on. Look out for more events in 2025.

[Research Support Games Day](#)

Monday 12 February 2024, 14:00-16:00 UK time

The aim of this event is to provide attendees with the opportunity to learn and discuss games-based tools and methods that are relevant to supporting researchers. For example, games that help to train researchers about Open

Access, copyright, research data management or documenting impact. Information and registration [here](#)

Reading recommendations

[Research Culture Initiatives in the UK](#)

UKRI commissioned [Vitae](#), [ShiftInsight](#) and [UKRN](#) to conduct a comprehensive review of research culture in the UK. The report presents a framework for research culture, together with key findings and recommendations. It includes opportunities and considerations for good practice exchange.

[Open Science 2.0: Towards a truly collaborative research ecosystem](#)

An international team of authors led by Robert Thibault provide an overview of open science initiatives including methods transparency, scholarly communication, team science, and research culture. There is also a personal perspective from UKRN's very own Marcus Munafò. Warning - the fact that this article is part of the PLOS Biology **20th** Anniversary Collection may make some readers (and this newsletter contributor) feel very old indeed.

[Registered Report editorial](#)

Registered Reports are increasingly being adopted across the Nature Portfolio of journals. This month sees the first publication of a Registered Report in the journal Nature Climate Change.

[Improving the transparency and reliability of observational studies through registration](#)

In this recent BMJ Analysis Florian Naudet and colleagues argue that routine

registration of observational research is needed and suggest how current processes can be adapted to facilitate it.

Online resources

[ReproducibiliTeach](#) is an online course where students watch a video and then use their new knowledge in a task. The content is produced by Tracey Weissgerber (meta-researcher at the QUEST Center for Responsible Research, Berlin Institute of Health at Charité) and René Bernard (Value and Open Science Coordinator, NeuroCure Cluster of Excellence).

[OpenAlex](#)

OpenAlex is a free global index of researchers, research institutions, citations, scholarly journals and the research ecosystem. It is provided by [OurResearch](#), a nonprofit organization dedicated to making research open.

You've read right to the end. We love you. Happy Valentine's Day!

Image credit: Bruno - Pixabay

Get involved

We'd love to hear from you. Let us share what you've been doing. Would you like to be a guest editor? Get in touch contact@ukrn.org

